

High Altitude Isopoda, Arachnida and Myriapoda in the Old World (supplementa and corrigenda 2008-2016)

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Abstract: After the publication of my monograph (BERON, 2008) appeared many new papers containing data on Arachnida and Myriapoda found in the Old World at or above 2200 m. In this supplement are added 12 sp. of Opiliones, 37 sp. of spiders, and 74 sp. of Diplopoda. Several changes occurred in the taxonomy of some groups, following taxonomic revisions. Several genera of Opiliones are no more in Phalangidae, but in Sclerosomatidae, Fuhrmanodesmidae became synonyme of Trichopolydesmidae, etc. "Palpatores" are now distributed between the suborders Eupnoi and Dyspnoi. Several specialists, and especially Golovatch, published many new taxa of high mountain Diplopoda. Again Golovatch synonymized several genera of Diplopoda (*Martensosoma*, *Nepalomorpha*, *Parorthomorpha*, *Armolites*, *Orophosoma*), known from the high mountains, under *Delartrum* Attems. For many taxa has been "raised" the upper limit of distribution and they have been published from other mountains.

Key Words: Arachnida, Myriapoda, high altitude, Old World, supplementa, corrigenda

Underlined are taxa not included in the monograph of BERON (2008)

The mountain systems of the Old World and the Isopoda, Arachnida and Myriapoda recorded therein

Pyrenees and the mountains of Iberian

Peninsula

Diplopoda

New ref.: GILGADO et al. (2015)

Chordeumatida

Fam. **Opisthocheiridae**

Ceratosphys *cryodeserti* Gilgado, Mauriès et

Enghoff – Sierra Nevada

Alps

Arachnida

Araneae

New ref.: TANASEVITCH (2011a, 2011b, 2013)

Fam. Linyphiidae

Agyneta *nigripes* (Simon) – 1900 – 2580 m

Erigone *remota* L. Koch – 2650 m

E. tenuimana Simon – up to 2580 m

Caucasus

Arachnida

Opiliones

New ref.: SNEGOVAYA (1999, 2004, 2010, 2014)

Fam. Phalangidae

Odiellus *bieniaszi* Kulczynski – up to 3000 m

Opilio *lederi* Roewer – up to 3000 m

O. *parietinus* (De Geer) – up to 3000 m

(Azerbaijan)

O. *redikorzevi* Roewer – 2400 m

Phalangium *opilio* L. – up to 3000 m

Ph. *punctipes* L. Koch – up to 3000 m

Araneae

New ref.: LOGUNOV & DEMIR (2006)

Fam. Thomisidae

Xysticus *bacurianensis* Mcheidze – 3000 m

(Azerbaijan), 2900 m (Georgia)

Myriapoda

Diplopoda

New ref.: GOLOVATCH, EVSYUKOV & REIP (2016)

Fam. Polydesmidae

Brachydesmus *assimilis* Lohmander – 2800 m

B. *kalischewskyi* Lignau – 2400 m

Polydesmus *lignau* Lohmander – 2800 m

Mountains of Turkey, Armenia, Lebanon, Iran, Kopet Dagh and Arabian Peninsula

Arachnida

Araneae

New ref.: LOGUNOV & DEMIR (2006), SEYYAR,
DEMIR, TOPÇU & TAŞDEMİR (2006)

Fam. Gnaphosidae

Phaeoedus braccatus (L. Koch) – 2300 m
(Erciyes)

Fam. Thomisidae

Xysticus bacurianensis Mcheidze – 2200 m
X. cristatus (Clerck) – 2200 m

Mountains of Afghanistan, Pakistan, Karakorum, Tibet, Pamir, Kunlun and Tien Shan (from the border between Iran and Afghanistan to 120° E)

Arachnida

Opiliones

New or omitted ref.: STAREGA (1986), STAREGA & SNEGOVAYA (2008a)

Eupnoi

Fam. Phalangidae

Homolophus gricenkoj Starega et Snegovaya – 2000–3000 m (Tadjikistan)

H. andreevae Starega et Snegovaya – up to 4670 m (Pamir)

Pamiropilio naukat Starega et Snegovaya – 3000–3300 m (Kyrgyzstan, Alayskiy Hrebet)

Dyspnoi

Fam. Nemastomatidae

Mediostoma (?) *pamiricum* Starega, 1986–3100 m (Pamir)

Araneae

New ref.: KOK, LOTZ & HADDAD (2004), TANASEVITCH (2011b)

Fam. Linyphiidae

Acartauchenius himalayensis Tanasevitch – 2500 m (Karakorum)

Agyneta nigripes (Simon) – 2635 m (Karakorum)

Archaraeoncus prospiciens (Thorell) – 2700–3000 m (Karakorum)

Caviphantes pseudosaxetorum Wunderlich – 550–2500 m (Karakorum)

Ceratinella wideri (Thorell) – 2500–3100 m (Karakorum)

Gongylidiellum confusum Thaler – 1600–2700 m (Karakorum)

Maso sundevalli (Westring) – 2200 – 2300 m (Karakorum)

Pelecopsis indus Tanasevitch – 2300 m (Karakorum)

Piniphantes himalayensis (Tanasevitch) – 2800 m (Karakorum)

Porrhomma pygmaeum (Blackwall) – 2480 m (Karakorum)

Prinerigone vagans (Audouin) – 1700–2700 m (Karakorum)

cotargus pilosus Simon – 1400–2450 m (Karakorum)

Tiso incisus Tanasevitch – 1300–2500 m (Karakorum)

Acari

New ref.: DANIEL (1973), DANIEL, STEKOLNIKOV, HAKIMITABAR & SABOORI (2010), JING, SOLHOY, WANG, VOLLAN & XU (2005)

Acari, known from the described area at or above 2200 m (suppl.):

Acariformes

Prostigmata

Fam. Trombiculidae

Microtrombicula gratiosa Schluger et Kudryashova – Hindu Kush, 2950 m

M. similata Schluger et Amanguliev – Hindu Kush, 3080 m

M. vacillata Fernandes et Kulkarni – Hindu Kush, 3080 m

Neotrombicula lubrica Kudryashova – Hindu Kush, 2950–3990 m

Leptotrombidium silvaticum Hushcha et Schluger – Hindu Kush, 2782 m

Montivagum dihumeralis (Traub et Nadchatram) – Hindu Kush, 3990 m

M. latum (Schluger et Kudryashova) – Hindu Kush, 2950–3990 m

M. raropinne (Schluger) – Hindu Kush, 3100 m

Euschoengstia meshhedensis Kudryashova, Neronov et Farhang-Azad – Hindu Kush, 2950 – 3990 m

Brunehaldia lucida Schluger – Hindu Kush, 2950 m

Shunsennia oudemansi (Schluger) – 2950 – 4550 m

Himalaya

(East of Indus and South and West of Tzangpo, or Brahmaputra)

New research:

B. Petrov collected many different animals during his several climbing expeditions in the Himalaya.

Notes on Isopoda, Arachnida and Myriapoda

Arachnida

Scorpiones

New ref.: ZAMBRE, SANAP & MIRZA (2014)

Fam. Euscorpiidae

Scorpiops spitiensis Zambre, Sanap et Mirza – Himalaya, 4200 m

Araneae

New ref.: JASTRZEBSKI, 2010, 2011, OVTCHINNIKOV, AHMAD & INAYATULLAH (2008), TANASEVITCH (2011b), WANG & ZHU (2008)

Some spiders in the Himalaya found at or above 2200 m after 2008 are:

Fam. Amaurobiidae

Himalmartensius ausobskyi Wang et Zhu – 1770-3000 m

H. martensi Wang et Zhu – 1400-2900 m

H. nepalensis Wang et Zhu – 1000-2600 m

Fam. Gnaphosidae

Gnaphosa pakistanica Ovtchinnikov, Ahmad et Inayatullah – 4100 m

Fam. Linyphiidae

Anguliphantes nepalsioides Tanasevitch – 2500-2600 m

Gongyliidiellum confusum Thaler – up to 3200 m (Kashmir)

Indophantes tonglu Tanasevitch – 2500-2700 m

Pelecopsis indus Tanasevitch – 2250 m

Tapinocyboides bengalensis Tanasevitch – 3100 m

Tiso incisus Tanasevitch – 1900 – 2450 m

T.(?) indianus Tanasevitch – 2500 – 2600 m

Walckenaeria martensi Wunderlich = *W. nepalensis* Wund. (syn. by Tanasevitch, 2011b)

Acari

New and omitted ref.: DANIEL (1973), DANIEL & STEKOLNIKOV (2009), DANIEL, STEKOLNIKOV, HAKIMITABAR & SABOORI (2010), ERMILOV & MARTENS (2014), FERNANDES & KULKARNI (2003)

Some of the Acari, found in Himalaya at or above 2200 m after 2008, are:

Acariformes

Prostigmata

Fam. Trombiculidae

Brunehaldia lucida Schluger – 2950 m

Cheladonta ikaoensis Sasa et al. – 3450-4000 m

Doloisia vlastae Daniel et Stekolnikov – 3450 m

Euschoengastia meshhedensis Kudryashova et al. – 2950-3990 m

Leptotrombidium angkamii Daniel et Stekolnikov – 3450-3900 m

L. silvaticum Hushcha et Schluger – 2782 m

Microtrombicula gratiosa Schluger et Kudryashova – 2950 m

M. similata Schluger et Amanguliev – 3080 m

M. vacillata Fernandes et Kulkarni – 3080 m

Montivagum dihumeralis (Traub et Nadchatram) – 3990 m

M. latum (Schluger et Kudryashova) – 2950-3990 m

M. raropinne (Schluger) – up to 3100 m

Neotrombicula kounickyi Daniel et Stekolnikov – 3450-4000 m

N. lubrica Kudryashova – 1090-3990 m

N. turkestanica Kudryashova – 3990 m

Shunsennia oudemansi (Schluger) – 1800-4100 m

Trombiculindus mehtai Fernandes et Kulkarni – 3450-4600 m

Myriapoda

Chilopoda

Scolopendromorpha

Fam. Scolopendridae

Scolopendra canidens Newport – 2400 m

Diplopoda

New ref.: GOLOVATCH (2014, 2015b, 2016), GOLOVATCH, NZOKO FIEMAPONG & VANDENSPIEGEL (2015), GOLOVATCH, VANDENSPIEGEL & SEMENYUK (2016)

Polydesmida (restructuring)

Fam. Trichopolydesmidae (syn. Fuhrmannodesmidae)

Fam. Paradoxosomatidae

Anoplocephalus martensi Golovatch – up to 3600 m (Nepal)

Beronodesmoides lobatus Golovatch – 4600 m (Nepal)

B. montigena Golovatch 3550 m (Nepal)

B. typicus Golovatch – 3400 m (Nepal)

B. anteriporus Golovatch – 3350 m (Nepal)

B. martensi Golovatch – 2700 m (Nepal)

Beronodesmus latispinosus Golovatch – up to 3500 m (Nepal)

B. longispinosus Golovatch – up to 4270 m (Nepal)

B. pallidus Golovatch – 4100 m (Nepal)

B. gorkhalis Golovatch – up to 3600 m (Nepal)

B. latispinosus Golovatch – 3150 m (Nepal)

B. serratus Golovatch et al. – up to 3500 m (Nepal)

B. sinuatospinus Golovatch – 2250 m (Nepal)

Delarthrum (= *Armolites*) *chulingensis* (Golovatch) – up to 3700 m

D. similis (Golovatch) – up to 2700 m

D. communicans (Golovatch) – up to 2650 m

D. spiniger (Attems) – 2200 m (India)

Hirtodrepanum latigonopum Golovach – up to 2700 m

Kaschmiriosoma pleuroptera Attems – up to 2800 m (Pakistan)

Martensosoma silvestre Golovatch – up to 2600 m

M. schawalleri Golovatch – up to 2150 m

M. splendens Golovatch – up to 2150 m

Delarthrum (= *Nepalomorpha*) *hirsutum* (Golovatch) – up to 4100 m

D. kuznetzovi (Golovatch) – up to 3000 m

D. arunensis (Golovatch) – up to 2150 m

Delarthrum (= *Orophosoma*) *simulans* (Carl) – up to 3700 m

D. hingstoni (Carl) – up to 3400 m

D. fechteri (Golovatch) – up to 3150 m

Paranedypopus martensi Golovatch – up to 3600 m

P. similis Golovatch – up to 3000 m
P. cylindricus Carl – up to 2850 m
P. affinis Golovatch – up to 2700 m
P. schawalleri Golovatch – up to 2150 m
Delarthrum (= *Parorthomorpha*) *tuberculatum*
 (Golovatch) – up to 3300 m
D. spectabilis (Golovatch) – up to 2650 m
D. tergalis Golovatch – up to 2650 m
D. nyakensis Golovatch – up to 2450 m
D. philosophicum Golovatch – up to 2450 m
Touranella himalayensis Golovatch – up to 2700 m
Substrongylosoma montigena Carl – up to
 2300 m (India)

**Mountains of Southeast Asia China (south of
 Yang Tse), Thailand, Vietnam, Taiwan, Philippine
 Islands, Indonesia and Malaysia**

Opiliones

New ref.: MARTENS (2016)

Fam. Nemastomatidae

Sinostoma yunnanicum Martens – 3800 m
 (China, Yunnan)

Araneae

New ref.: DANKITTIPAKUL & JOCQUÉ (2006),
 ZONSTEIN & MARUSIK (2012)

Fam. Zodariidae

Cydrela pristina Dankittipakul et Jocqué – 1630
 – 2500 m (Thailand, Doi Inthanon)

Fam. Nemesiidae

Raveniola montana Zonstein et Marusik – up
 4300 m (China, Yunnan)

R. sangrila Zonstein et Marusik – up 4300 m
 (China, Yunnan)

R. songi Zonstein et Marusik – up 4300 m
 (China, Yunnan)

R. yunnanensis Zonstein et Marusik – up 4300
 m (China, Yunnan)

Myriapoda

Diplopoda

New ref.: GOLOVATCH (2015, 2016), KORSÓS,
 ENGHOFF & CHANG (2008)

Diplopoda found at or above 2200 m after 2008:

Glomerida

Fam. Glomeridae

Hyleoglomeris robusta Attems – 1800-2400 m
 (Vietnam)

H. electa Silvestri – 2300 – 2400 m (Vietnam)

Platydesmida

Fam. Platydesmidae

Platydesmus camptotrichus Attems – 700-2400
 m (Vietnam)

P. variegatus Attems – 1500 – 2400 m
 (Vietnam)

Spirobolida

Fam. Pachybolidae

Trigoniulus brachysternus Attems – 1400 – 2400
 m (Vietnam)

Siphonophorida

Fam. Siphonophoridae

Teratognathus robusta Attems – 1000 – 2400 m
 (Vietnam)

Polydesmida

Fam. Paradoxosomatidae

Belousoviella kabaki Golovatch – 3360 m
 (China, Sichuan)

Cleptomorpha sumatrana Golovatch – 1400 –
 2600 m (Sumatra)

Gonobelus pentaspinus Golovatch – 2475 m
 (China, Sichuan)

Hedinomorpha nigra Golovatch – 4000 m
 (China, Sichuan)

H. subnigra Golovatch – 3910 m (China, Yunnan)

H. montana Golovatch – 3575 m (Yunnan)

H. proxima Golovatch – 3570 m (Yunnan)

H. yunnanensis Golovatch – 3480 m (Yunnan)

H. reducta Golovatch – 2900 m (Sichuan)

H. jeekeli Golovatch – 2600 m (China, Shaanxi)

Inversispina erectispina Golovatch – 4036 m
 (China, Sichuan), 3130 m (Yunnan, idem)

Kronopolites biagrilectus Hoffman – 3210 m
 (China, Yunnan)

K. semirugosus Golovatch – 2955 m (China,
 Sichuan)

K. rugosus Golovatch – 2400 m (China, Yunnan)

Sellanucheza typica Golovatch – 3155 m (Sichuan)

Sigipinius grahami Hoffman – 4205 m (China,
 Sichuan)

S. simplex Golovatch – 4195 m (China, Sichuan)

S. complex Golovatch – 4120 m (China, Sichuan)

S. campanuliformis Golovatch – 3910 m (China,
 Yunnan)

S. dentiger Golovatch – 3570 m (China, Yunnan)

S. kabaki Golovatch – 3550 m (China, Xinjiang
 Uygur Prov.)

Tectoporus beroni Golovatch – 1400-2600 m
 (Sumatra)

T. aberrans Golovatch – 1400-2600 m (Sumatra)

T. beshkovi Golovatch – 1400-2600 m (Sumatra)

Tylopuso schawalleri Golovatch 2700 m (China,
 Yunnan)

Fam. Cryptodesmidae

Trichopeltis Pocock – up to 2400 m (*T. kometis*
 Attems, Vietnam)

Fam. Polydesmidae

Epanerchodus fuscus Golovatch – 3325 m
 (China, Yunnan)

- Fam. Xystodesmidae
Riukiaria spatuliformes Golovatch – 2525 m
 (China, Sichuan)
- Fam. Cryptodesmidae
Trichopeltis kometis (Attems) – 1500 – 2400 m
 (Vietnam)
- Polyzoniida**
 Fam. Siphonocryptidae
Siphonocryptus compactus Pocock – up to 2600 m, Sumatra (ENGHOFF & GOLOVATCH, 1995)
Hirudicryptus taiwanensis Korsós, Enghoff et Chang – up to 2200 m, Taiwan, KORSÓS, ENGHOFF & CHANG, 2008)
- Mountains of New Guinea, Bismarck Archipelago and the Solomon Islands**
- Chilopoda**
 New ref.: SHILEYKO & STOEVE (2016)
- Scolopendromorpha**
 Fam. Cryptopidae
Cryptops doriae Pocock – up to 3150 m (PNG)
C. nepalensis Lewis, 1999-2700 m (PNG)
C. spinipes Pocock – 2260-2600 m (PNG)
Cryptops sp. – 3150 m (PNG)
- Diplopoda** (restructuring)
 New ref.: GOLOVATCH & STOEVE (2010, 2011, 2014, 2014a),
- Polydesmida**
 Fam. Paradoxosomatidae
Caloma agametum Chamberlin – 2300 m (PNG)
Eustrongylosoma curtipes Golovatch et Stoev – 2300 m (PNG)
E. beroni Golovatch et Stoev – 2300 m (PNG)
E. finimtel Golovatch et Stoev – [2300 m] (PNG)
E. tumbuna Golovatch et Stoev – 2980 m (PNG)
E. masalai Golovatch et Stoev – [2300 m] (PNG)
E. papua Golovatch et Stoev – [2300 m] (PNG)
E. tifalmin Golovatch et Stoev – [2300 m] (PNG)
Silvattia jeekeli Golovatch et Stoev – 2300 m (PNG)
Tectorporus fugilil Golovatch et Stoev – 2600 m (PNG)
T. bispinosus Golovatch et Stoev – 2600 m (PNG)
T. moniliformis Golovatch et Stoev – 2600 m (PNG)
T. spiniger Golovatch et Stoev – 2300 m (PNG)
T. wilhelmicus Golovatch et Stoev – 3610 m (PNG)
- Fam. Opisotretidae
Opisotretus beroni Golovatch, Geoffroy, Stoev et Vanden Spiegel – Papua New Guinea
- Fam. Cryptodesmidae
Astrolabius hoffmani Golovatch, Stoev et Vandenspiegel – 2600 m (Papua New Guinea)
 Altai, the Mountains of Siberia, Mongolia and the Far East
- Araneae**
 New ref.: TANASEVITCH (2013)
- Fam. Linyphiidae
Araeoncus crassiceps (Westring) – 1800-2800 m (Altai)
A. vorkutensis Tanasevitch – 500-2450 m (Altai)
Bathylinyphia major (Kul.) – 600-2500 m (Altai)
Bolyphantes distichus (Tanasevitch) – up to 2300 m (Altai)
Dicymbium facetum (L. Koch) – up to 3800 m (Altai)
Erigone arctica maritima Kul. – 2500-3000 m
E. arctica Chamberlin et Ivie – 2400-3100 m (Altai)
E. cristatopalpus Simon – up to 2400 m (Altai)
E. remota L. Koch – up to 3100 m (Altai)
Gonatium pacificum Eskov – 2400-3100 m (Altai)
Halorates altaicus Tanasevitch – 2000-2500 m (Altai)
Hilaila glacialis (Thorell) – 2400-3100 m (Altai)
H. meridionalis Tanasevitch – 200-3300 m (Altai)
Improphantes improbulus (Simon) – 1400-2500 m (Altai)
Incestophantes bonus Tanasevitch – 2100-2800 m (Altai)
I. breviamellus Tanasevitch – 2600-2800 m (Altai)
I. tuvensis Tanasevitch – 2600-3000 m (Altai)
Islandiana falsifica (Keyserling) – 2400-3100 m (Altai)
Macrargus rufus (Wider) – 2000-2500 m (Altai)
Mughiphantes sobrioides Tanasevitch – 2600-2800 m (Altai)
Oedothorax mongolensis (Heimer) – 2000-800 m (Altai)
Oreoneta eskovi Saaristo et Marusik – 1700-2800 m (Altai)
Pelecopsis dorniana Heimer – 1600-2200 m (Altai)
P. palmgreni Marusik et Eshyunin – 1400-2200 m (Altai)
Porrhomma pallidum Jackson – 2100-2500 m (Altai)
Scotinotylus antennatus (O. Pickard-Cambridge) – 2000-2300 m (Altai)

- S. protervus* (L. Koch) – 1800-3000 m (Altai)
Semljicola angulatus (Holm) – 1650-2200 m (Altai)
S. latus (Holm) – 1350-2200 m (Altai)
Silometopus uralensis Tanasevitch – 1700 – 2200 m (Altai)
Stemonyphantes altaicus Tanasevitch – 1300-2500 m (Altai)
Tenuiphantes suborientalis Tanasevitch – 2200-2500 m (Tuva)
Thyreostenius parasiticus (Westring) – 500-2200 m (Altai)
Typhlochrestoides baikalensis Eskov – 1600-2200 m (Altai)
Walckenaeria capito (Westring) – 1700-2500 m (Altai)
W. katanda Marusik, Hippa et Koponen – 1500-2200 (Altai)
W. esyunini Tanasevitch – 2600 m (Altai)

Mountains in West Equatorial Africa

Opiliones

New ref.: STARĘGA & SNEGOWAYA (2008b)

Fam. Phalangidae

- Camerobunus okucola* Staręga et Snegovaya – 2200-2800 m (Cameroon)

Diplopoda

New ref.: GOLOVATCH, NZOKO FIEMAPONG & VANDENSPIEGEL (2015)

Fam. Pyrgodesmidae

- Monachodesmus armorum* Golovatch et al. – 2320 m (Cameroon)

- Udodesmus camerunensis* Golovatch et al. – 2320 m (Cameroon)

- Urodesmus cornutus* Golovatch et al. – 2320 m (Cameroon)

ISOPODA in the Old World known at or above 2200 m and the highest living Isopoda in the World (supplementa)

New ref.: no new information

ARACHNIDA

SCORPIONES in the Old World known at or above 2200 m and the highest living Scorpiones in the World (supplementa)

New ref.: OCHOA et al. (2011), ZAMBRE, SANAP & MIRZA (2014)

Order Scorpiones. Maximal altitude (corrected): 4910 m in Peru, 4600 m in the Himalaya.

Fam. Euscorpiidae, Scorpipinae

- Scorpiops* Peters – up to 4200 m (*S. spitiensis* Zambre, Sanap et Mirza, Himalaya)

OCHOA, OJANGUREN AFFILASTRO, MATTONI & PRENDINI (2011) described six new species of

genus *Orobothriurus* Maury, 1976 and made a list of the Scorpion species recorded above 3000 m in the Andes. This list contains 39 sp. of the genera *Orobothriurus*, *Bothriurus*, *Pachkutej*, and *Brachistosternus* (Bothriuridae, up to 4910 m in Peru), *Tityus* (Buthidae, up to 4200 m in Bolivia), *Hadruroides* (Juridae, up to 3379 m in Peru) and *Teuthraustes* (Chactidae, 3300 m in Ecuador). According to these authors, the former world maximum altitude, recorded for “*Orobothriurus*” *crassimanus* – actually *Pachakutej crassimanus* (Maury, 1976) by LOURENÇO (1997) – 5560 m at Nevado Huascarán (Peru) – is based on misidentification and erroneous locality data. These authors accept as highest record of scorpions the newly described *Orobothriurus huascarán* at 4910 m in Peru. In 1977 I have visited the area above Paron lake and climbed on the slopes of Huandoy over 5000 m. The environment was free of snow and ice, with forests of *Polylepis* and it is quite possible that scorpions will be found higher than 5000 m. In Asia scorpions have been found (with certainty) up to 4600 m (*Tibetiomachus himalayensis* Lourenço et Qi, 2006, Liochelidae), in Africa – up to 3500 m (*Uroplectes fischeri* Tullgren, 1910, Meru, Buthidae).

PSEUDOSCORPIONES found in the Old World at or above 2200 m and the highest found Pseudoscorpions in the World (supplementa)

No new information

OPILIONES in the Old World known at or above 2200 m and the highest living Opiliones in the World (supplementa)

New ref.: DAS & BASTAWADE (2006), MARTENS (2016), MARTENS & CHEMINI (1988), SNEGOWAYA (1999, 2004, 2010, 2014), STARĘGA (1986), STARĘGA & SNEGOWAYA (2008a, 2008b)

Eupnoi

Fam. Phalangidae

- Camerobunus* Staręga et Snegovaya – up to 2800 m (*C. okucola* Staręga et Snegovaya, Cameroon)

Homolophus Banks (*Euphalangium* Roewer) – up to 4670 m (*H. andreevae* Staręga et Snegovaya, Pamir), 3000 m (*H. gricenkoi* Staręga et Snegovaya, Tadjikistan), 3000 m (*H. [Euphalangium] martensi* (Das et Bastawade), Indian Himalaya)

Odiellus Roewer – up to 3000 m (*O. bieniaszi* Kulczynski, Caucasus)

Opilio Herbst – up to 3000 m (*O. lederi* Roewer), 2400 m (*O. redikorzevi* Roewer)(Caucasus)

Pamiropilio Staręga et Snegovaya – up to 3300 m (*P. naukat* Staręga et Snegovaya, Kyrgyzstan, Alayskiy Hrebet)

Phalangium L.– up to 3000 m (*Ph. punctipes* L. Koch, Caucasus)

Dyspnoi

Fam. Nemastomatidae

Mitostoma Roewer – up to 3100 m (*Mitostoma* ? – Pamir)

Sinostoma Martens – up to 3800 m (*S. yunnanicum* Martens, China, Yunnan)

Fam. Trogulidae

Anelasmoccephalus Simon – up to 2450 m (*A. osellai* Martens et Chemini, Appenines), 2200 m (*A. cambridgei* Westwood, Alps)

Species of Opiliones, known from the Old World at and above 3500 m (restructuring of the list)

Homolophus Banks (syn. *Euphalangium nordenskiöldi* (L. Koch)(Phalangiidae) – 5600 m (Karakorum)

Himalphalangium palpale Roewer (Phalangiidae) – 5540 m (Nepal)

Homolophus panpema Suzuki (Phalangiidae) – 5200 m (Nepal)

H. luteum Suzuki (Phalangiidae) – 5200 m (Nepal)

Octozaleptus harai Suzuki (Sclerosomatidae) – 5200 m (Nepal)

Leiobunum mirum Roewer (Phalangiidae) – 5200 m (Nepal)

Sabaconidae gen. sp. – > 5000 m (Nepal)

?*Opilio* sp. (Phalangiidae) – 4800 m (Karakorum)

Homolophus andreevae Starega et Snegovaya (Phalangiidae) – 4670 m (Pamir)

Hypoxestus accentuatus Sörensen (Assamiidae) – 4600 m (Kilimanjaro)

Rhampsinitus bettoni Pocock (Sclerosomatidae) – 4600 m (Kilimanjaro)

?*Phalangium* sp. (Phalangiidae) – 4500 m (Karakorum)

Egaenus (= *Diabunus*) *laevipes* (di Caporiacco) (Phalangiidae) – 4400 m (Karakorum)

Sabacon dhaulagiri Martens (Sabaconidae) – 4250 m (Nepal)

Biantes pernepalicus Martens (Biantidae) – 4250 m (Nepal)

Himalphalangium dolpoense Martens (Phalangiidae) – 4200 m (Nepal)

Micrassamula thak Martens (Assamiidae) – 4200 m (Nepal)

Hypoxestus holmi Goodnight et Goodnight (Assamiidae) – 4200 m (East Africa)

Gyoides himaldispersus Martens (Sclerosomatidae) – 4200 m (Nepal)

Odontobunus armatus(Sörensen)(Phalangiidae) – 4200 m (Kenya), 4000 m (Kilimanjaro)

Opilio almasyi Roewer (Phalangiidae) – 4200 m (Karakorum)

O. nigradorsum di Caporiacco (Phalangiidae) – 4200 m (Karakorum)

Ereca undulata Sörensen (Assamiidae) – 4025 m (Ruwenzori)

E. simulator Sörensen (Assamiidae) – 4000 m (Kilimanjaro)

Metaereca abnormis Roewer (Assamiidae) – 4000 m (Ruwenzori)

Hypoxestus patellaris Sörensen (Assamiidae) – 4000 m (Ruwenzori)

Metabiantes punctatus Sörensen (Biantidae) – 4000 m (Kilimanjaro)

Guruia africana Karsch (Phalangiidae) – 4000 m (Kilimanjaro)

G. frigescens Loman (Phalangiidae) – 4000 m (East Africa)

Rhampsinitus ? mesomelas Sörensen (Phalangiidae) – 4000 m (Kilimanjaro)

Ereca maculata Roewer (Assamiidae) – 3975 m (Kilimanjaro)

Dhaulagirius altitudinalis Martens (Phalangodidae) – 3950 m (Nepal)

Cristina pachylomera Simon (Phalangiidae) – 3870 m (Ruwenzori; 3658 m, Semien)

Rhampsinitus discolor Karsch (Sclerosomatidae) – 3870 m (Ruwenzori)

Himaldroma altus Martens (Sclerosomatidae) – 3830 m (Nepal)

Rhampsinitus salti Roewer (Phalangiidae) – 3800 m (Kilimanjaro)

Gyoides maximus Martens (Sclerosomatidae) – 3800 m (Nepal)

Sinostoma yunnanicum Martens (Nemastomatidae) – 3800 m (Yunnan)

Odontobunus africanus Roewer (Phalangiidae) – 3770 m (Kivu)

Gyoides gandaki Martens (Sclerosomatidae) – 3760 m (Nepal)

Bunochelis spinifera Lucas (Phalangiidae) – 3711 m (Tenerife)

Eudasylobus infuscatus Lucas (Phalangiidae) – 3650 m (Atlas)

Rilaena triangularis Herbst (Phalangiidae) – 3650 m (Atlas)

Biantes thakkhali Martens (Biantidae) – 3640 m (Nepal)

Randilea scabricula Roewer (Assamiidae) – 3630 m (Elgon)

Metabiantes trifasciatus Roewer (Biantidae) –

3600 m (Meru)

Mitopus glacialis Heer (Phalangiidae) – 3600 m (Alps)

Dacnopilio scopulatus Lawrence (Phalangiidae) – 3600 m (Meru)

Egaenus tibetanus Roewer (Phalangiidae) – 3600 m (Karakorum)

Harmanda medioimmicans Martens (Sclerosomatidae) – 3600 m (Nepal)

Simienatus scotti Roewer (Assamiidae) – 3505 m (Semien, Ethiopia)

Metabiantes convexus Roewer (Biantidae) – 3500 m (Ruwenzori)

Ereca lata Sørensen (Assamiidae) – 3500 m (Kilimanjaro)

E. affinis Sørensen (Assamiidae) – 3500 m (Kilimanjaro)

E. modesta Sørensen (Assamiidae) – 3500 m (Kilimanjaro)

Hypoxestus mesoleucus Sørensen (Assamiidae) – 3500 m (Kilimanjaro)

Harmanda latehippiata Martens (Sclerosomatidae) – 3500 m (Nepal)

H. nigrolineata Martens (Sclerosomatidae) – 3500 m (Nepal)

Pokhara yodai Suzuki (Sclerosomatidae) – 3500 m (Nepal)

Rhampsinitus soerenseni Starega (= *Rh. pictus* Sørensen) (Phalangiidae) – 3500 m (Meru)

Maximal altitudes of Harvestmen (Opiliones), living above 2200 m in the Old World

1 – Triaenonychidae – up to 2500 m

2 – Oncopodidae – up to 2600 m

3 – Podoctidae – up to 2410 m

4 – Biantidae – up to 4250 m

5 – Assamiidae – up to 4600 m

6 – Phalangiidae – up to 5600 m

7 – Sclerosomatidae – up to 5200 m

8 – Ischyropsalididae – up to 2700 m

9 – Sabaconidae – more than 5000 m

10 – Nemastomatidae – up to 3800 m

ARANEAE found in the Old World at or above 2200 m and the highest

found Araneae in the World (supplementa)

New ref.: DANKITTIPAKUL & JOCQUÉ (2006), LOGUNOV & DEMIR (2006), JASTRZĘBSKI, 2010a, 2010b, 2011, OVTCHINNIKOV, AHMAD & INAYATULLAH (2008), SEYYAR, DEMIR, TOPÇU & TAŞDEMİR (2006), TANASEVITCH (2011b, 2013), ZONSTEIN & MARUSIK (2012)

Fam. Amaurobiidae

Himalmartensius Wang et Zhu – up to 3000

m (*H. ausobskyi* Wang et Zhu, 2900 m (*H. martensi* Wang et Zhu), 2600 m (*H. nepalensis* Wang et Zhu), all from Nepal

Fam. Linyphiidae

Acartauchenius Simon – up to 2500 m (*A. himalayensis* Tanasevitch, Karakorum)

Agyneta Hull – up to 2635 m (*A. nigripes* Simon, Karakorum)

Anguliphantes Saaristo et Tanasevitch – up to 2600 m (*A. nepalsioides* Tanasevitch)

Araeoncus Simon – up to 2800 m (*A. crassiceps* Westring, Altai), 2450 m (*A. vorkutensis* Tanasevitch, Altai)

Archaraeoncus Tanasevitch – up to 3000 m (*A. prospiciens* Thorell, Karakorum)

Bathylinyphia Eskov – up to 2500 m (*B. major* Kul., Altai)

Bolyphantes C.L. Koch – up to 2300 m (*B. distichus* Tanasevitch, Altai)

Caviphantes Oi – up to 2500 m (*C. pseudosaxetorum* Wunderlich, Karakorum)

Ceratinella Emerton – up to 3100 m (*C. wideri* Thorell, Karakorum)

Dicymbium Menge – up to 3800 m (*D. facetum* L. Koch, Altai)

Erigone Audouin – up to 3100 m (*E. arctica* Chamberlin et Ivie, Altai; *E. remota* L. Koch, Altai; 2650 m, Alps), 3000 m (*E. arctica maritima* Kul., Altai), 2400 m (*E. cristatopalpus* Simon, Altai)

Gonatum Menge – up to 3100 m (*G. pacificum* Eskov, Altai)

Gongyliellum Simon – up to 3200 m (*G. confusum* Thaler, Kashmir), 2700 m, Karakorum)

Halorates Hull – up to 2500 m (*H. altaicus* Tanasevitch, Altai)

Hilaila Simon – up to 3300 m (*H. meridionalis* Tanasevitch, Altai), 3100 m (*H. glacialis* (Thorell, Altai)

Indophantes Tanasevitch et Saaristo – up to 2700 m (*I. tonglu* Tanasevitch (Himalaya)

Improphantes Saaristo et Tanasevitch – up to 2500 m (*I. improbulus* Simon, Altai)

Incestophantes Tanasevitch – up to 3000 m (*I. tuvensis* Tanasevitch, Altai), 2800 m (*I. bonus* Tanasevitch, *I. brevilamellus* Tanasevitch, Altai)

Islandiana Braendegaard – up to 3100 m (*I. falsifica* Keyserling, Altai)

Macrargus Dahl – up to 2500 m (*M. rufus* Wider, Altai)

Maso Simon – up to 2300 m (*M. sundevalli* Westring, Karakorum)

Mughiphantes Saaristo et Tanasevitch – up to 2800 m (*M. sobrioides* Tanasevitch, Altai)

Oedothorax Bertkau – up to 2800 m (*Oe. mongolensis* Heimer, Altai)

Oreoneta Kulczynski – up to 2800 m (*O. eskovi* Saaristo et Marusik, Altai)

Pelecopsis Simon – up to 2300 m (*P. indus* Tanasevitch, Karakorum), 2200 m (*P. dorniana* Heimer, *P. palmgreni* Marusik et Eyunin, Altai)

Piniphantes Saaristo et Tanasevitch – up to 2800 m (*P. himalayensis* Tanasevitch, Karakorum)

Porrhomma Simon – up to 2500 m (*P. pallidum* Jackson, Altai), 2480 m (*P. pygmaeum* Blackwall, Karakorum)

Prinerigone Wunderlich – up to 2700 m (*P. vagans* Audouin, Karakorum)

Scotargus Simon – up to 2450 m (*S. pilosus* Simon, Karakorum)

Scotinotylus Simon – 3000 m (*S. protervus* L. Koch, Altai), 2300 m (*S. antennatus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, Altai)

Semljicola Strand – 2200 m (*S. angulatus* Holm, *S. latus* Holm Altai)

Silometopus Simon – up to 2200 m (*S. uralensis* Tanasevitch, Altai)

Stemonyphantes Menge – 2500 m (*S. altaicus* Tanasevitch, Altai)

Tapinocyboides Wiehle – up to 3100 m (*T. bengalensis* Tanasevitch)

Tenuiphantes Tanasevitch – up to 2500 m (*T. suborientalis* Tanasevitch, Tuva)

Thyreostenius Simon – up to 2200 m (*Th. parasiticus* Westring, Altai)

Tiso Simon – up to 2500 m (*T. incisus* Tanasevitch, Karakorum)

T.(?) indianus Tanasevitch – 2500 – 2600 m

Typhlochrestoides Eskov – up to 2200 m (*T. baikalensis* Eskov, Altai)

Walckenaeria Blackwall – up to 2600 m (*W. esyunini* Tanasevitch, Altai), 2500 m (*W. capito* Westring, Altai), 2200 m (*W. katanda* Marusik, Hippa et Koponen, Altai)

Walckenaeria martensi Wunderlich = *W. nepalensis* Wund. (syn. by Tanasevitch, 2011b)

Fam. Zodariidae

Cydrela Thorell – up to 2500 m (*C. pristina* Dankittipakul et Jocqué, Thailand, Doi Inthanon)

Fam. Nemesiidae

Raveniola Zonstein – up to 4300 m (*R. montana* Zonstein et Marusik, *R. sangrila* Zonstein et Marusik, *R. songi* Zonstein et Marusik, *R. yunnanensis* Zonstein et Marusik, China, Yunnan)

Fam. Gnaphosidae

Gnaphosa Latreille – up to 4100 m (*G. pakistanic* Ovtchinnikov, Ahmad et Inayatullah, Pakistan),

Phaeoedus Simon – up to 2300 m (*Ph. braccatus* L. Koch, Erziyes, Turkey)

Fam. Thomisidae

Xysticus Walckenaer – up to 3000 m (*X. bacurianensis* Mcheidze, Azerbaijan), 2900 m (Georgia), 2200 m (*X. cristatus* Clerck, Turkey)

Species of Araneae, known from the Old World at and above 3500 m (supplement to the list)

Raveniola montana Zonstein et Marusik (Nemesiidae) – 4300 m (China, Yunnan)

R. shangrila Zonstein et Marusik (Nemesiidae) – 4300 m (China, Yunnan)

R. songi Zonstein et Marusik (Nemesiidae) – 4300 m (China, Yunnan)

R. yunnanensis Zonstein et Marusik (Nemesiidae) – 4300 m (China, Yunnan)

Gnaphosa pakistanic Ovtchinnikov, Ahmad et Inayatullah (Gnaphosidae) – 4100 m (Pakistan)

ACARI found in the Old World at or above 2200 m and the highest found Acari in the World (supplementa)

New or omitted ref.: DANIEL (1973, 2015), DANIEL & STEKOLNIKOV (2009), DANIEL, STEKOLNIKOV, HAKIMITABAR & SABOORI (2010), ERMILOV & MARTENS (2014), FERNANDES & KULKARNI (2003)

Acariformes

Sarcoptiformes

Acaridida – correction: the highest Prostigmata found is on 3500 m (Himalaya)

Oribatida – correction: the highest Oribatida is found on 5800 m (Himalaya)

Fam. Scheloribatidae

Perscheloribates Hammer – up to 2800 m (*P. nepalensis* Ermilov et Martens, Nepal)

Trombidiformes

Prostigmata – correction: the highest Prostigmata is found on 5100 m (Himalaya)

Fam. Trombiculidae

Aboriginesia Kudryashova becomes synonyme of *Xinjiangsha* Wen et Shao

Brunehaldia Vercammen-Grandjean et Kolebinova – up to 2950 m (*B. lucida* Schluger, Hindu Kush)

Cheladonta Lipovsky, Crossley et Loomis – up to 4000 m (*Ch. ikaoensis* Sasa et al., Nepal)

Doloisia Oudemans – up to 3450 m (*D. vlastae* Daniel et Stekolnikov, Nepal)

Euschoengastia Ewing – up to 3990 m (*E. mes-hhedensis* Kudryashova et al., Hindu Kush)

Leptotrombidium Nagayo et al. – up to 3900 m (*L. angkamii* Daniel et Stekolnikov, Nepal), 2782 m

(*L. silvaticum* Hushcha et Schluger, Hindu Kush)

Microtrombicula Ewing – up to 3080 m (*M. similata* Schluger et Amanguliev, *M. vacillata* Fernandes et Kulkarni), 2950 m (*M. gratiosa* Schluger et Kudryashova, all from Hindu Kush)

Montivagum Kudryashova – up to 3990 m (*M. dihumerales* Traub et Nadchatram, *M. latum* (Schluger et Kudryashova) (Hindu Kush), 3100 m (*M. raropinne* (Schluger, Hindu Kush)

Neotrombicula Hirst – up to 4000 m (*N. kounickyi* Daniel et Stekolnikov, Nepal), 3990 m (*N. lubrica* Kudryashova, Hindu Kush, *N. turkestanica* Kudryashova)

Shunsennia Jameson et Toshioka – up to 4550 m (*Shunsennia oudemansi* Schluger, Hindu Kush; 4100 m,)

Trombiculindus Radford – up to 4600 m (*T. mehtai* Fernandes et Kulkarni, Nepal)

Species of Prostigmata (Trombidiformes), known from the Old World at and above 3500 m (supplement to the list)

Trombiculindus mehtai Fernandes et Kulkarni (Trombiculidae) – 4600 m (Nepal)

Shunsenia oudemansi Schluger (Trombiculidae) – 4100 m (Hindu Kush)

Neotrombicula kounickyi Daniel et Stekolnikov (Trombiculidae) – 4000 m (Himalaya)

Ch. ikaoensis Sasa et al. (Trombiculidae) – 4000 m (Nepal)

Euschoengastia meshhedensis Kudryashova et al. (Trombiculidae) – 3990 m (Hindu Kush)

Montivagum dihumerales Traub et Nadchatram (Trombiculidae) – 3990 m (Hindu Kush)

M. latum (Schluger et Kudryashova) (Trombiculidae) – 3990 m (Hindu Kush)

Leptotrombidium angkamii Daniel et Stekolnikov (Trombiculidae) – 3900 m (Nepal)

DIPLOPODA found in the Old World at or above 2200 m and the highest found Diplopoda in the World (supplement)

New Ref.: ENGHOF & GOLOVATCH (1995), GOLOVATCH (2013, 2014, 2015a, 2015b, 2016), GOLOVATCH, EVSYUKOV & REIP (2016), GOLOVATCH & STOEV (2009, 2010, 2011, 2014a, 2014b), GOLOVATCH, VANDENSPIEGEL & SEMENYUK (2016), GOLOVATCH, NZOKO FIEMAPONG & VANDENSPIEGEL (2010, 2015), KORSÓS, ENGHOF & CHANG (2008), NEFEDIEV, NEFEDIEVA & JANKOWSKI (2015)

Glomerida

Fam. Glomeridae

Hyleoglomeris Verhoeff – up to 2400 m (*H. robusta* Attems, *H. electa* Silvestri, Vietnam)

Chordeumatida

Fam. **Opisthocheiridae**

Ceratospys cryodeserti Gilgado, Mauriès et Enghoff – (Sierra Nevada)

Platydesmida

Fam. **Platydesmidae**

Platydesmus Cook – up to 2400 m (*P. camptotrichus* Attems, *P. variegatus* Attems, Vietnam)

Polydesmida

Fam. Fuhrmannodesmidae becomes synonyme of Trichopolydesmidae (after GOLOVATCH, 2013)

Fam. Paradoxosomatidae – up to 4600 m (Nepal)

Anoplocephalus Schaeffer – up to 3600 m (*A. martensi* Golovatch, Nepal)

Belousoviella Golovatch – up to 3360 m (*B. kabaki* Golovatch, Sichuan)

Beronodesmoides Golovatch – up to 4600 m (*B. lobatus* Golovatch, Nepal), 3550 m (*B. montigena* Golovatch, Nepal), 3400 m (*B. typicus* Golovatch, Nepal), 3350 m (*B. anteriporus* Golovatch, Nepal), 2700 m (*B. martensi* Golovatch, Nepal)

Beronodesmus Golovatch – up to 4270 m (*B. longispinosus* Golovatch, Nepal), 4100 m (*B. pallidus* Golovatch, Nepal), 3600 m (*B. gorkhalis* Golovatch, Nepal), 3500 m (*B. serratus* Golovatch et al., *B. latispinosus* Golovatch et al., Nepal), 2650 m (*B. martensi* Golovatch et al., Nepal), 2250 m (*B. sinuatospinus* Golovatch, Nepal)

Caloma Chamberlin – up to 2300 m (*C. agame-tum* Chamberlin, Papua New Guinea)

Cleptomorpha Golovatch – up to 2600 m (*C. sumatrana* Golovatch, Sumatra)

Delarthrum Attems (syn. *Nepalomorpha* Golovatch, *Pararthromorpha* Golovatch, *Martensosoma* Golovatch, *Armolites* Golovatch, *Orophosoma* Jeekel) – up to 3250 m (*D. tenuitergale* Golovatch, Nepal), 3100 m (*D. typicum* Golovatch, Nepal); according to GOLOVATCH (2014), in the list in BERON (2008) should be changed the following species:

Delarthrum [*Martensosoma*] *silvestre* (Golovatch), *Delarthrum* [*Martensosoma*] *schawalleri* (Golovatch), *Delarthrum* [*Martensosoma*] *splendens* (Golovatch), *Delarthrum* [*Nepalomorpha*] *hirsutum* (Golovatch), *Delarthrum* [*Nepalomorpha*] *kuznetzovi* (Golovatch), *Delarthrum* [*Nepalomorpha*] *arunense* (Golovatch), *Delarthrum* [*Pararthromorpha*] *tuberculatum* (Golovatch), *Delarthrum* [*Pararthromorpha*] *spectabile* (Golovatch, 2650 m, Nepal, GOLOVATCH, 2016), *Delarthrum* [*Pararthromorpha*] *tergale* (Golovatch), *Delarthrum* [*Pararthromorpha*] *nyakense* (Golovatch), *Delarthrum* [*Pararthromorpha*] *philosophica* (Golovatch), *Delarthrum*

[*Armolites*] *chulingensis* (Golovatch), *Delartrum* [*Armolites*] *simile* (Golovatch), *Delartrum* [*Armolites*] *communicans* (Golovatch), *Delartrum* [*Armolites*] *spiniger* (Attems, India), *Delartrum* [*Orophosoma*] *simulans* (Carl), *Delartrum* [*Orophosoma*] *hingstoni* (Carl), *Delartrum* [*Orophosoma*] *fechteri* (Golovatch) (all others from Nepal)

Eustrongylosoma Silvestri – up to 2980 m (*E. tumbuna* Golovatch et Stoev), 2300 m (*P. beroni* Golovatch et Stoev, *E. curtipes* Golovatch et Stoev, Golovatch et Stoev, *E. masalai* Golovatch et Stoev, *E. finimtel* Golovatch et Stoev, *E. maculatum* Golovatch et Stoev, *E. papua* Golovatch et Stoev, *E. tifalmin* Golovatch et Stoev), all from Papua New Guinea

Gonobelus Attems – up to 2475 m (*G. pentaspinus* Golovatch, China, Sichuan)

Hedinomorpha Verhoeff – up to 4000 m (*H. nigra* Golovatch, China, Sichuan), 3910 m (*H. subnigra* Golovatch, China, Yunnan), 3575 m (*H. montana* Golovatch, Yunnan), 3570 m (*H. proxima* Golovatch, Yunnan), 3480 m (*H. yunnanensis* Golovatch, Yunnan), 2900 m (*H. reducta* Golovatch, Sichuan), 2600 m (*H. jeekeli* Golovatch, China, Shaanxi)

Hirtoderpanum Golovatch – up to 2600 m (*H. latigonopum* Golovatch, Nepal)

Inversispina Zhang – up to 4036 m (*I. erectispina* Golovatch, China, Sichuan), 3130 m (Yunnan, idem)

Kronopolites Attems – up to 3210 m (*K. biagri-lectus* Hoffman, China, Yunnan), 2955 m (*K. semirugosus* Golovatch, China, Sichuan), 2400 m (*K. rugosus* Golovatch, China, Yunnan)

Sellanucheza Enghoff, Golovatch et Nguyen Duc – up to 3155 m (*S. typica* Golovatch, Sichuan)

Sigipinius Hoffman – up to 4205 m (*S. grah-ami* Hoffman, China, Sichuan), 4195 m (*S. simplex* Golovatch, China, Sichuan), 4120 m (*S. complex* Golovatch, China, Sichuan), 3910 m (*S. campanuliformis* Golovatch, China, Yunnan), 3570 m (*S. dentiger* Golovatch, China, Yunnan), 3550 m (*S. kabaki* Golovatch, China, Xinjiang Uygur Prov.)

Tectorporus Carl – up to 3610 m (*T. wilhelmicus* Golovatch et Stoev, Papua New Guinea), 2980 m (*T. fugilil* Golovatch et Stoev, Papua New Guinea), 2600 m (*T. aberrans* Golovatch, *T. beroni* Golovatch, *T. beshkovi*, Sumatra; *T. fugilil* Golovatch et Stoev, *T. bispinosus* Golovatch et Stoev, *T. moniliformis* Papua New Guinea), 2300 m (*T. spiniger* Golovatch et Stoev, Papua New Guinea)

Tylopus Jeekel – up to 2700 m (*T. schawalleri* Golovatch, China, Yunnan)

Fam. Cryptodesmidae

Astrolabius Verhoeff – up to 2600 m (*A. hoffmani* Golovatch, Stoev et Vandenspiegel, Papua New Guinea)

Trichopeltis Pocock – up to 2400 m (*T. kometis* Attems, Vietnam)

Fam. Pyrgodesmidae

Monachodesmus Silvestri – up to 2320 m (*M. armorum* Golovatch et al., Cameroon)

Udodesmus Cook – up to 2320 m (*U. camerunensis* Golovatch et al., Cameroon)

Urodesmus Porat – up to 2320 m (*U. cornutus* Golovatch et al., Cameroon)

Fam. Polydesmidae

Brachydesmus Heller – up to 2800 m (*B. assimilis* Lohmander, 1936, Caucasus), 2400 m (*B. kalschewskyi* Lignau, Caucasus)

Epanerchodus Attems – up to 3325 m (*E. fuscus* Golovatch, China, Yunnan)

Polydesmus Latreille – up to 2800 m (*P. lignau* Lohmander, Caucasus)

Fam. Xystodesmidae

Riukiaria Attems – up to 2525 m (*R. spatuliformes* Golovatch, China, Sichuan)

Fam. Opisotretidae

Opisotretus *beroni* Golovatch, Geoffroy, Stoev et Vanden Spiegel (Papua New Guinea)

Order **Polyzoniida**

Fam. Siphonocryptidae

Siphonocryptus Pocock – up to 2600 m (*S. compactus* Pocock (Sumatra, ENGHOFF & GOLOVATCH, 1995)

Hirudicryptus Enghoff et Golovatch – up to 2200 m (*H. taiwanensis* Korsós, Enghoff et Chang (Taiwan, KORSÓS, ENGHOFF & CHANG, 2008)

Species of DIPLOPODA, known from the Old World at and above 3500 m (restructuring of the list in BERON, 2008)

Nepalmatoiulus *ivanloebli* Enghoff (Julida, Julidae) – 4800 m (Nepal)

Beronodesmoides *lobatus* Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 4600 m (Nepal)

Uixenus sp. (Polyxenida, Polyxenidae) – 4550 m (Nepal)

Hingstonia *variata* Golovatch (Polydesmida, Trichopolydesmidae = Fuhrmannodesmidae) – 4500 m (Nepal)

Anaulaciulus *niger* Korsós (Julida, Julidae) – 4500 m (Nepal)

A. bilineatus Korsós (Julida, Julidae) – 4300 m (Nepal)

Beronodesmus *longispinosus* Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 4270 m (Nepal)

Usbekodesmus sp. (Polydesmida, Polydesmidae) – 4250 m (Nepal)

Sigipinius grahami Hoffman (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – up to 4205 m (China, Sichuan)

Sigipinius simplex Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 4195 m (China, Sichuan)

Sphaeroparia petarberoni Mauriès et Heymer (Polydesmida, Trichopolydesmidae = Fuhrmannodesmidae) – 4200 m (Ruwenzori)

Sigipinius complex Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 4120 m (China, Sichuan)

Beronodesmus pallidus Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 4100 m (Nepal)

Delarthrum (= *Nepalomorpha*) *hirsutum* (Golovatch) (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 4100 m (Nepal)

Kashmireumanepalensis Mauriès (Chordeumatida, Kashmireumatidae) – 4100 m (Nepal)

Nepalella sp. (Chordeumatida, Megalotylidae) – 4100 m (Nepal)

Inversispina erectispina Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 4036 m (China, Sichuan)

Hedinomorpha nigra Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 4000 m (China, Sechuan)

Usbekodesmus sacer Golovatch (Polydesmida, Polydesmidae) – 4000 m (Nepal)

Hingstonia gogonema Golovatch (Polydesmida, Trichopolydesmidae = Fuhrmannodesmidae) – 4000 m (Buthan)

Anaulaciulus acaudatus Korsós (Julida, Julidae) – 3990 m (Sikkim)

Sigipinius campanuliformis Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3910 m (China, Yunnan)

Hedinomorpha subnigra Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3910 m (China, Yunnan)

Tianella daamsae Shear (Chordeumatida, Cleidogonidae) – 3900 m (Nepal)

Nepalella gunsa Shear (Chordeumatida, Megalotylidae) – 3800 m (Nepal)

Nepalmatoiulus hyalilobus Enghoff (Julida, Julidae) – 3800 m (Nepal)

Delarthrum (= *Armolites*) *chulingensis* (Golovatch) (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3700 m (Nepal)

Sigipinius dentiger Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3570 m (China, Yunnan)

Anaulaciulus tibetanus Korsós (Julida, Julidae) – 3700 m (Tibet)

Hingstonia fittkau Golovatch (Polydesmida, Trichopolydesmidae = Fuhrmannodesmidae) – 3650 m (Nepal)

H. sympatrica Golovatch (Polydesmida, Trichopolydesmidae = Fuhrmannodesmidae) – 3650 m (Nepal)

H. serrata Golovatch (Polydesmida, Trichopolydesmidae = Fuhrmannodesmidae) – 3600 m (Nepal)

Tectoporus wilhelmicus Golovatch et Stoev (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3610 m (Papua New Guinea)

Beronodesmus gorkhalis Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3600 m (Nepal)

Anoplocephalus martensi Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3600 m (Nepal)

Dolichoilulus canariensis Brölemann (Julida, Julidae) – 3600 m (Nepal)

Nepalmatoiulus mauriesi Enghoff (Julida, Julidae) – 3600 m (Nepal)

Polydesmus (Polydesmida, Polydesmidae) – 3600 m (Tenerife)

Hedinomorpha montana Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3575 m (China, Yunnan)

Hedinomorpha proxima Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3570 m (China, Yunnan)

Sigipinius kabaki Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3550 m (China, Xinjiang Uygur Prov.)

Beronodesmoides montigena Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3550 m (Nepal)

Beronodesmus serratus Golovatch, VandenSpiegel et Semenyuk (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3500 m (Nepal)

Beronodesmus latispinosus Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3500 m (Nepal)

Nepalella deharvengi Mauriès (Chordeumatida, Megalotylidae) – 3500 m (Nepal)

Stemmiulus sjostedti Attems (Stemmiulida, Stemmiulidae) – 3500 m (Meru)

Hingstonia beatae Golovatch (Polydesmida, Trichopolydesmidae = Fuhrmannodesmidae) – 3500 m (Nepal)

Sphaeroparia minuta Attems (Polydesmida, Trichopolydesmidae = Fuhrmannodesmidae) – 3500 m (Meru)

Hedinomorpha yunnanensis Golovatch (Polydesmida, Paradoxosomatidae) – 3480 m (China, Yunnan)

Ceratospys simoni Ribaut (Craspedosomatida, Opisthocheiridae) – 3460 m (Sierra Nevada)

Janetschekella valesiaca (Faès) (= *nivalis* Schubart) (Craspedosomatida, Craspedosomatidae) – 3450 m (Alps)

Re-calculated figures for the number of some Isopoda, Arachnida and Myriapoda recorded in the Old World at or higher than 2200 m

Scorpiones – from 28 to 29 sp.

Opiliones – from 294 to 305 sp.

Araneae – from 1340 to 1381 sp.

Acari Trombidiformes – added 12 sp. of Trombiculidae

Chilopoda – from 159 to 160 sp.

Diplopoda – from 294 to 365 sp.; added are also the order Polyzoniida, the families Platydesmidae, Xystodesmidae, Opisotrettidae and Siphonocryptidae

and 24 genera. Many corrections are made also in the lists of high altitude taxa in different areas.

Total inhabitants of altitudes over 2200 m in the Old World: 3927 (formerly 3789) sp.

The tendency, called by us “taxogradient”, remains valid.

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Високопланински Isopoda, Arachnida и Myriapoda в Стария свят (допълнения и поправки 2008-2016)

Петър БЕРОН

(Резюме)

След излизането на моята монография (BERON, 2008) бяха публикувани много нови данни и извършени някои корекции на по-старата информация върху високопланинските Isopoda, Arachnida и Myriapoda в Стария свят. Това наложи настоящото първо допълнение. С така ревизираните данни броят на известните видове от някои групи във високите планини се изменя както следва:

Scorpiones – от 28 на 29 в.

Opiliones – от 293 на 306 в.

Araneae – от 1340 на 1381 в.

Acari Trombidiformes – добавят се 12 в. от сем. Trombiculidae

Diplopoda – от 294 на 365 в.

Общ брой на изоподите, паякоподобните и многоножките в стария свят, познати над 2200 m: 3927 вида (според BERON, 2008-3789)